

The Distribution of Composites in Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT)

Charles Kusniec

charleskusniec@icloud.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1146-7847>

First text: 20 October 2023

version: 29 December 2023 19:46:02

Abstract: In this study, we conduct a meticulous examination of the reasons underlying the hyperbolic and parabolic distributions of composite numbers in multiplication tables. Each Variant Multiplication Table (VMT) is conceptualized as a rotational transformation of the standard Full Multiplication Table (FMT), further delineated in ‘The Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (HSP)’ [28]. These transformations are shown to conserve the fundamental geometric characteristics of number distribution, explicitly preserving the hyperbolic and parabolic patterns inherent in the spatial arrangement of composite numbers. Our analysis elucidates the mathematical structures and symmetries underpinning these distributions, offering new insights into the nature of composite numbers within these transformed multiplication frameworks.

Keywords: Multiplication Tables, Primes and Composites, Number Theory.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: 11A41, 11T06, 11B2, 11B375.

Copyright © 2020 - 2023 by the Author. This is an Open Access paper distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

1. Introduction.

To master mathematics, our head must look forward and be bigger than the body. It is insane when the head looks at the body before looking forward.

The study titled 'The SOM Numbers (Part I)' [23] uncovered various categories of tables based on each of the CG quadratic sequences. From my perspective, the most innovative and perplexing tables are those derived from the Full Multiplication Table (FMT) [28], as presented in the Mersenne Forum (<https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=646493&postcount=9>). These variations have been named Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT). It is remarkably surprising to observe that the multiplication table, one of humanity's earliest mathematical tools and a fundamental concept in early education, exhibits an endless array of variations.

In this study, we will unveil a new series of tables, elucidating how and why all products in the Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT) are distributed in both parabolic and hyperbolic patterns. This exploration not only deepens our understanding of the MT's inherent mysteries but also highlights the intricate interplay between fundamental mathematical structures.

2. Background: Quadratic Parameters of the Simplest Equation

The simplest general second-degree polynomial equation [27] has been defined as follows:

$$x = Y2[y] = \left(\frac{Y2[-1] - 2 * Y2[0] + Y2[1]}{2} \right) y^2 + \left(\frac{Y2[1] - Y2[-1]}{2} \right) y + Y2[0]$$

We will now proceed to determine all related parameters of this equation. For clarity in visualization of calculations and results, let us define:

$$Y2[-1] = x_1, Y2[0] = x_2, Y2[1] = x_3$$

Thus, the simplest second-degree polynomial equation can be rewritten as:

$$x = Y2[y] = \left(\frac{x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3}{2} \right) y^2 + \left(\frac{x_3 - x_1}{2} \right) y + x_2$$

2.1. Coefficient a

$$a = \frac{x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3}{2}$$

2.2. Coefficient b

$$b = \frac{x_3 - x_1}{2}$$

2.3. Coefficient c

$$c = x_2$$

2.4. Equation of the Y-Coordinates of the Symmetry Point

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{b}{2a} = -\frac{\frac{x_3 - x_1}{2}}{2\frac{x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3}{2}}$$

$$y_{sp} = -\frac{b}{2a} = \frac{-(x_3 - x_1)}{2(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

2.5. Equation of the X-Coordinates of the Symmetry Point

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{\Delta}{4a} = -\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} = -\frac{\left(\frac{x_3 - x_1}{2}\right)^2 - 4\left(\frac{x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3}{2}\right)x_2}{4\left(\frac{x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3}{2}\right)}$$

$$= \frac{4\left(\frac{x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3}{2}\right)x_2 - \left(\frac{x_3 - x_1}{2}\right)^2}{2(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)} = \frac{2(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)x_2 - \frac{(x_3 - x_1)^2}{4}}{2(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

$$= \frac{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)x_2 - (x_3 - x_1)^2}{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

$$= \frac{8x_1x_2 - 16x_2^2 + 8x_2x_3 - (x_1^2 + x_3^2 - 2x_1x_3)}{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

$$= \frac{8x_1x_2 - 16x_2^2 + 8x_2x_3 - x_1^2 - x_3^2 + 2x_1x_3}{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

$$= \frac{-x_1^2 - 16x_2^2 - x_3^2 + 8x_1x_2 + 8x_2x_3 + 2x_1x_3}{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

$$= \frac{-x_1^2 - (4x_2)^2 - x_3^2 + 2x_1(4x_2) + 2(4x_2)x_3 + 2x_1x_3}{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

Alternatively:

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{\Delta}{4a} = \frac{-x_1^2 - (4x_2)^2 - x_3^2 + 2x_1(4x_2) + 2(4x_2)x_3 + 2x_1x_3}{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

$$= \frac{-x_1^2 - (4x_2)^2 - x_3^2 + 2x_1(4x_2) + 2(4x_2)x_3 + 2x_1x_3}{16a}$$

Or,

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} = c - \frac{b^2}{4a} = x_2 - \frac{\left(\frac{x_3 - x_1}{2}\right)^2}{4\left(\frac{x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3}{2}\right)} = x_2 - \frac{\frac{(x_3 - x_1)^2}{4}}{2(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{\Delta}{4a} = -\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} = x_2 - \frac{(x_3 - x_1)^2}{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

2.6. The Parabolic-Hyperbolic Discriminant Equation.

Note that:

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} = -\frac{\Delta}{4a}$$

And,

$$x_{sp} = \frac{-x_1^2 - 16x_2^2 - x_3^2 + 8x_1x_2 + 8x_2x_3 + 2x_1x_3}{8(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}$$

$$= -\frac{x_1^2 + 16x_2^2 + x_3^2 - 8x_1x_2 - 8x_2x_3 - 2x_1x_3}{\frac{16(x_1 - 2x_2 + x_3)}{2}}$$

$$= -\frac{x_1^2 + 16x_2^2 + x_3^2 - 8x_1x_2 - 8x_2x_3 - 2x_1x_3}{16a}$$

$$x_{sp} = -\frac{\left(\frac{x_1^2 + 16x_2^2 + x_3^2 - 8x_1x_2 - 8x_2x_3 - 2x_1x_3}{4}\right)}{4a}$$

So,

$$\Delta = \frac{x_1^2 + 16x_2^2 + x_3^2 - 8x_1x_2 - 8x_2x_3 - 2x_1x_3}{4}$$

$$\Delta = \frac{x_1^2 + (4x_2)^2 + x_3^2 - 2x_1(4x_2) - 2(4x_2)x_3 - 2x_1x_3}{4}$$

2.7. The Hyperbolic-Hyperbolic Discriminant Equation.

We know that,

$$(X - Y - Z)^2 = X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 - 2XY - 2XZ + 2YZ$$

So,

$$X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 - 2XY - 2XZ - 2YZ = (X - Y - Z)^2 - 4YZ$$

Then,

$$X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 - 2XY - 2XZ - 2YZ = (X - Y - Z + 2\sqrt{YZ})(X - Y - Z - 2\sqrt{YZ})$$

Now, being $X = x_1, Y = 4x_2, Z = x_3$, then:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & x_1^2 + (4x_2)^2 + x_3^2 - 2x_1(4x_2) - 2x_1x_3 - 2(4x_2)x_3 \\
 & \quad = (x_1 - 4x_2 - x_3 + 2\sqrt{4x_2x_3})(x_1 - 4x_2 - x_3 - 2\sqrt{4x_2x_3}) \\
 & x_1^2 + (4x_2)^2 + x_3^2 - 2x_1(4x_2) - 2x_1x_3 - 2(4x_2)x_3 \\
 & \quad = (x_1 - 4x_2 - x_3 + 4\sqrt{x_2x_3})(x_1 - 4x_2 - x_3 - 4\sqrt{x_2x_3}) \\
 & x_1^2 + (4x_2)^2 + x_3^2 - 2x_1(4x_2) - 2x_1x_3 - 2(4x_2)x_3 \\
 & \quad = (x_1 - x_3 - 4(x_2 - \sqrt{x_2x_3}))(x_1 - x_3 - 4(x_2 + \sqrt{x_2x_3})) \\
 & x_1^2 + (4x_2)^2 + x_3^2 - 2x_1(4x_2) - 2x_1x_3 - 2(4x_2)x_3 \\
 & \quad = (x_1 - x_3 - 4\sqrt{x_2}(\sqrt{x_2} - \sqrt{x_3}))(x_1 - x_3 - 4\sqrt{x_2}(\sqrt{x_2} + \sqrt{x_3})) \\
 \Delta &= \frac{(x_1 - x_3 - 4\sqrt{x_2}(\sqrt{x_2} - \sqrt{x_3}))(x_1 - x_3 - 4\sqrt{x_2}(\sqrt{x_2} + \sqrt{x_3}))}{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

3. Exploring the Dynamic Interplay of Diagonals in MT

The variations of the FMT become more plausible when we identify that the $\pm 45^\circ$ diagonals, corresponding to the C003108 trio $\{0,0,0\}$ VMT Variant MT (<https://www.mersenneforum.org/showpost.php?p=646493&postcount=9>), represent the studied quadratic sequences, expressed in the form of (quadratic Numbers minus an element of the quadratic Numbers). At $\pm 45^\circ$ diagonals, the sequences have a second-degree coefficient $a = 1$, with the central starting area formed by the three sequences that make up the SOM numbers.

Similarly, this Numbers of quadratic sequences, initiated by the SOM numbers, is clearly visible in the central vertical columns of the C003133 trio $\{1,0,1\}$, SUB-type, $a=1$, Variant MT (VMT) 15x15 (<https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28116&page=2>), as explored in the Mersenne Forum. A 45-degree rotation was applied to the sequences that were originally inclined at 45 degrees.

Thus, by using the three sequences that form the SOM numbers as our reference point in the multiplication table, we begin to discern previously unexplored properties.

As we adjust the slope of the diagonal from 1: 1 to 1: *integer*, we increase the second-degree coefficient. This demonstrates the dynamic nature of the multiplication table and its complementarity to Pascal's Triangle, both forming the fundamental tools of polynomials. A vertical or horizontal line in the Multiplication Table produces a first-degree polynomial, while a diagonal produces a second-degree polynomial. A parabolic curve in the table results in a cubic Numbers, and so on.

Furthermore, the multiplication table embodies and translates all the properties of the method of differences, which is the mathematical foundation for the formation of polynomials. It also underpins the operational properties of integral calculus and derivatives.

Title: C001855 The Distribution of Composites in Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT) – Author: Charles

Another intriguing aspect that warrants further investigation is the distribution of composite numbers in the XY plane of the Multiplication Table. For instance, the distribution of the SOM numbers in 'C001169 The SMT in table format', studied in 'The Hyperbolic Sieve of Prime Numbers' [28], is illustrated in the subsequent figure:

Figure 1. C001169 The SMT in table format.

We show the highlighted area that is free of repetition from the diagonal of square numbers.

From the 45° diagonal line of the square numbers, we have the parallel diagonal line of the oblong numbers, then the diagonal line of the (square minus 1) numbers, and so on.

These 45° diagonals form the quadratic sequences of composite numbers in the form of $x = y(y \pm b_d)$.

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/357315535925392/>

<https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=2277189525783112&set=pcb.357315535925392>

#	SNYPO	OEIS	MT diag.	Name	Type	Hyperb. f≠0	Parab. f≠0	b d	CG equation f=0
1	C000800	https://oeis.org/A000290	$x = y \pm 0$	square - 0	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 0)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 0y$	0	$Y[y] = y^2 - 0$
2	C000900	https://oeis.org/A002378	$x = y \pm 1$	oblong - 0	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 1)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 1y$	1	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 0$
3	C000801	https://oeis.org/A005563	$x = y \pm 2$	square - 1	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 2)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 2y$	2	$Y[y] = y^2 - 1$
4	C000901	https://oeis.org/A028552	$x = y \pm 3$	oblong - 2	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 3)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 3y$	3	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 2$
5	C000802	https://oeis.org/A028347	$x = y \pm 4$	square - 4	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 4)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 4y$	4	$Y[y] = y^2 - 4$
6	C000902	https://oeis.org/A028557	$x = y \pm 5$	oblong - 6	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 5)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 5y$	5	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 6$
7	C000803	https://oeis.org/A028560	$x = y \pm 6$	square - 9	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 6)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 6y$	6	$Y[y] = y^2 - 9$
8	C000903	https://oeis.org/A028563	$x = y \pm 7$	oblong - 12	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 7)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 7y$	7	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 12$
9	C000804	https://oeis.org/A028566	$x = y \pm 8$	square - 16	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 8)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 8y$	8	$Y[y] = y^2 - 16$
10	C000904	https://oeis.org/A028569	$x = y \pm 9$	oblong - 20	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 9)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 9y$	9	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 20$
11	C000805	https://oeis.org/A098603	$x = y \pm 10$	square - 25	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 10)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 10y$	10	$Y[y] = y^2 - 25$
12	C000905	https://oeis.org/A119412	$x = y \pm 11$	oblong - 30	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 11)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 11y$	11	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 30$
13	C000806	https://oeis.org/A098847	$x = y \pm 12$	square - 36	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 12)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 12y$	12	$Y[y] = y^2 - 36$
14	C000906	https://oeis.org/A132759	$x = y \pm 13$	oblong - 42	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 13)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 13y$	13	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 42$
15	C000807	https://oeis.org/A098848	$x = y \pm 14$	square - 49	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 14)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 14y$	14	$Y[y] = y^2 - 49$
16	C000907	https://oeis.org/A132760	$x = y \pm 15$	oblong - 56	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 15)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 15y$	15	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 56$
17	C000808	https://oeis.org/A098849	$x = y \pm 16$	square - 64	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 16)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 16y$	16	$Y[y] = y^2 - 64$
18	C000908	https://oeis.org/A132761	$x = y \pm 17$	oblong - 72	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 17)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 17y$	17	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 72$
19	C000809	https://oeis.org/A098850	$x = y \pm 18$	square - 81	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 18)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 18y$	18	$Y[y] = y^2 - 81$
20	C000909	https://oeis.org/A132762	$x = y \pm 19$	oblong - 90	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 19)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 19y$	19	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 90$
21	C000810	https://oeis.org/A120071	$x = y \pm 20$	square - 100	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 20)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 20y$	20	$Y[y] = y^2 - 100$
22	C000910	https://oeis.org/A132763	$x = y \pm 21$	oblong - 110	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 21)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 21y$	21	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 110$
23	C000811	https://oeis.org/A132764	$x = y \pm 22$	square - 121	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 22)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 22y$	22	$Y[y] = y^2 - 121$
24	C000911	https://oeis.org/A132765	$x = y \pm 23$	oblong - 132	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 23)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 23y$	23	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 132$
25	C000812	https://oeis.org/A132766	$x = y \pm 24$	square - 144	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 24)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 24y$	24	$Y[y] = y^2 - 144$
26	C000912	https://oeis.org/A132767	$x = y \pm 25$	oblong - 156	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 25)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 25y$	25	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 156$
27	C000813	https://oeis.org/A132768	$x = y \pm 26$	square - 169	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 26)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 26y$	26	$Y[y] = y^2 - 169$
28	C000913	https://oeis.org/A132769	$x = y \pm 27$	oblong - 182	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 27)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 27y$	27	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 182$
29	C000814	https://oeis.org/A132770	$x = y \pm 28$	square - 196	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 28)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 28y$	28	$Y[y] = y^2 - 196$
30	C000914	https://oeis.org/A132771	$x = y \pm 29$	oblong - 210	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 29)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 29y$	29	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 210$
31	C000815	https://oeis.org/A132772	$x = y \pm 30$	square - 225	SUB	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 30)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 30y$	30	$Y[y] = y^2 - 225$
32	C000915	https://oeis.org/A132773	$x = y \pm 31$	oblong - 240	DES	$Y[y] = y(y \pm 31)$	$Y[y] = y^2 \pm 31y$	31	$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 240$

Figure 2. C001169 The MT $\pm 45^\circ$ quadratic diagonals sequences.

4. The Parabolic-Hyperbolic Distribution of Composite Numbers in the Multiplication Table (MT)

The 45-degree diagonal lines, represented by the equation $x = y \pm b_d$ in the FMT, intersect points with integer coordinates (x, y) , whose product results in integer elements that form the previously illustrated quadratic sequences.

For a better visualization of these sequences, refer to the diagonals in figure C000432, titled 'Map of the Triangular Multiplication Table (TMT)', available at https://oeis.org/wiki/User:Charles_Kusniec/themapofTMT.

As defined in <https://oeis.org/A334454>, (1) all prime numbers, including prime 1 [26], are distinct elements in the TMT, meaning they never repeat. (2) Any composite number always appears more than once in the TMT, leading to the presence of both 'distinct composites' and 'repeated composites' in the table.

Owing to the hyperbolic distribution of elements in the FMT, as studied in 'The Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (HSP)' [28] and the analyses of central pair of complementary divisors in 'Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework' [22], 'distinct composites' invariably appear in the quadratic sequences that generate the central pair of complementary divisors. For any distinct composite, this occurs in the quadratic Numbers in the form $Y[y] = y(y \pm b_d)$, where $b_d = b_{dm} = d_{c2} - d_{c1} = \text{https://oeis.org/A056737}[x]$. sequences <https://oeis.org/A333995> and <https://oeis.org/A333996> further elucidate the differences between 'distinct composites' and 'repeated composites' in the TMT.

For example, consider the number $x = d_1 * d_2 = 36 = 6 * 6 = 4 * 9 = 3 * 12 = 2 * 18 = 1 * 36$. Since element 36 has 5 pairs of complementary divisors, there are 5 quadratic sequences in the form $Y[y] = y(y \pm b_d)$. This is because we have, in ascending order, the 5 values of b_d : $\{6 - 6 = 0, 9 - 4 = 5, 12 - 3 = 9, 18 - 2 = 16, 36 - 1 = 35\}$. Consequently, the element 36 is part of the following quadratic sequences:

$$Y[y] = y(y) = 6 * 6$$

$$Y[y] = y(y \pm 5) = 4(4 + 5) = 9(9 - 5)$$

$$Y[y] = y(y \pm 9) = 3(3 + 9) = 12(12 - 9)$$

$$Y[y] = y(y \pm 16) = 2(2 + 16) = 18(18 - 16)$$

$$Y[y] = y(y \pm 35) = 1(1 + 35) = 36(36 - 1)$$

x_sp	0	-6.25	-20.25	-64	-306.25	0	-306.25	-64	-20.25	-6.25
y_sp	0	-2.5	-4.5	-8	-17.5	0	17.5	8	4.5	2.5
f	0	-3	-5	-8	-18	0	17	8	4	2
type	SUB	DES	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	DES
a	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
b		5	9	16	35		-35	-16	-9	-5
c										
20	400	500	580	720	1100	400	-300	80	220	300
19	361	456	532	665	1026	361	-304	57	190	266
18	324	414	486	612	954	324	-306	36	162	234
17	289	374	442	561	884	289	-306	17	136	204
16	256	336	400	512	816	256	-304	0	112	176
15	225	300	360	465	750	225	-300	-15	90	150
14	196	266	322	420	686	196	-294	-28	70	126
13	169	234	286	377	624	169	-286	-39	52	104
12	144	204	252	336	564	144	-276	-48	36	84
11	121	176	220	297	506	121	-264	-55	22	66
10	100	150	190	260	450	100	-250	-60	10	50
9	81	126	162	225	396	81	-234	-63	0	36
8	64	104	136	192	344	64	-216	-64	-8	24
7	49	84	112	161	294	49	-196	-63	-14	14
6	36	66	90	132	246	36	-174	-60	-18	6
5	25	50	70	105	200	25	-150	-55	-20	0
4	16	36	52	80	156	16	-124	-48	-20	-4
3	9	24	36	57	114	9	-96	-39	-18	-6
2	4	14	22	36	74	4	-66	-28	-14	-6
1	1	6	10	17	36	1	-34	-15	-8	-4
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-1	1	-4	-8	-15	-34	1	36	17	10	6
-2	4	-6	-14	-28	-66	4	74	36	22	14
-3	9	-6	-18	-39	-96	9	114	57	36	24
-4	16	-4	-20	-48	-124	16	156	80	52	36
-5	25	0	-20	-55	-150	25	200	105	70	50
-6	36	6	-18	-60	-174	36	246	132	90	66
-7	49	14	-14	-63	-196	49	294	161	112	84
-8	64	24	-8	-64	-216	64	344	192	136	104
-9	81	36	0	-63	-234	81	396	225	162	126
-10	100	50	10	-60	-250	100	450	260	190	150
-11	121	66	22	-55	-264	121	506	297	220	176
-12	144	84	36	-48	-276	144	564	336	252	204
-13	169	104	52	-39	-286	169	624	377	286	234
-14	196	126	70	-28	-294	196	686	420	322	266
-15	225	150	90	-15	-300	225	750	465	360	300
-16	256	176	112	0	-304	256	816	512	400	336
-17	289	204	136	17	-306	289	884	561	442	374
-18	324	234	162	36	-306	324	954	612	486	414
-19	361	266	190	57	-304	361	1026	665	532	456
-20	400	300	220	80	-300	400	1100	720	580	500

Figure 3. C001528 Example for the Number 36 in the TMT with $f \geq 0$.

The corresponding equations with an offset $f = 0$ are, respectively:

$$Y[y] = y^2$$

$$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 6$$

$$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 20$$

$$Y[y] = y^2 - 64$$

$$Y[y] = y^2 - y - 306$$

y_sp	0	0.5	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0.5
f	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
type	SUB	DES	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	SUB	DES	DES
a ^e	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
b ^e	0	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-1	0	-1	-1
c ^e	0	-6	-20	-64	-306	0	-306	-64	-20	-6
20	400	374	360	336	74	400	74	336	360	374
19	361	336	322	297	36	361	36	297	322	336
18	324	300	286	260	0	324	0	260	286	300
17	289	266	252	225	-34	289	-34	225	252	266
16	256	234	220	192	-66	256	-66	192	220	234
15	225	204	190	161	-96	225	-96	161	190	204
14	196	176	162	132	-124	196	-124	132	162	176
13	169	150	136	105	-150	169	-150	105	136	150
12	144	126	112	80	-174	144	-174	80	112	126
11	121	104	90	57	-196	121	-196	57	90	104
10	100	84	70	36	-216	100	-216	36	70	84
9	81	66	52	17	-234	81	-234	17	52	66
8	64	50	36	0	-250	64	-250	0	36	50
7	49	36	22	-15	-264	49	-264	-15	22	36
6	36	24	10	-28	-276	36	-276	-28	10	24
5	25	14	0	-39	-286	25	-286	-39	0	14
4	16	6	-8	-48	-294	16	-294	-48	-8	6
3	9	0	-14	-55	-300	9	-300	-55	-14	0
2	4	-4	-18	-60	-304	4	-304	-60	-18	-4
1	1	-6	-20	-63	-306	1	-306	-63	-20	-6
0	0	-6	-20	-64	-306	0	-306	-64	-20	-6
-1	1	-4	-18	-63	-304	1	-304	-63	-18	-4
-2	4	0	-14	-60	-300	4	-300	-60	-14	0
-3	9	6	-8	-55	-294	9	-294	-55	-8	6
-4	16	14	0	-48	-286	16	-286	-48	0	14
-5	25	24	10	-39	-276	25	-276	-39	10	24
-6	36	36	22	-28	-264	36	-264	-28	22	36
-7	49	50	36	-15	-250	49	-250	-15	36	50
-8	64	66	52	0	-234	64	-234	0	52	66
-9	81	84	70	17	-216	81	-216	17	70	84
-10	100	104	90	36	-196	100	-196	36	90	104
-11	121	126	112	57	-174	121	-174	57	112	126
-12	144	150	136	80	-150	144	-150	80	136	150
-13	169	176	162	105	-124	169	-124	105	162	176
-14	196	204	190	132	-96	196	-96	132	190	204
-15	225	234	220	161	-66	225	-66	161	220	234
-16	256	266	252	192	-34	256	-34	192	252	266
-17	289	300	286	225	0	289	0	225	286	300
-18	324	336	322	260	36	324	36	260	322	336
-19	361	374	360	297	74	361	74	297	360	374
-20	400	414	400	336	114	400	114	336	400	414

Figure 4. C001528 Example for the Number 36 in the TMT with $f = 0$.

Would it be too trivial a question for a mathematics Olympiad to ask why, when transforming sequences $Y[y] = y(y \pm b_d)$ with an offset $f = 0$, the 'c' coefficient always results in a square or oblong number? This becomes obvious to those who understand the study 'Shift, Symmetry, and Asymmetry in Polynomial Sequences' [27]. Perhaps if we expand the question to explain when squares or oblongs appear, it will make the question a little more challenging...

Since the number 36 is a composite appearing in more than one quadratic Numbers in the form $Y[y] = y(y \pm b_d)$ in the TMT, the 'distinct composite 36' appears only when $b_d = b_{dm} = 0$. That is, only the 36 resulting from $6 * 6$, which occurs in the Numbers $Y[y] = y(y) = 6 * 6$, is classified as a 'distinct composite'. All other four 36 elements occurring in the TMT are 'repeated composites'.

Obviously, all 36 elements in the TMT lie on the hyperbola $xy = 36$.

Only the point (6,6), producing the element 36 in the Numbers $x = y(y)$ and situated on the diagonal $x = y + 0$ in the TMT, yields the distinct composite 36.

The coordinates (9,4), (12,3), (18,2), and (36,1) yield the repeated element 36. All these five 36 elements lie on the same hyperbolic curve $xy = 36$, which also intersects with the line $x = y + 0$ at the point (6,6).

In fact, this line is the extreme form of a 45-degree parabola with a latus rectum of 0.

This is because all points also belong to the 45-degree rotated parabolas (quadratics) in the form $x^2 + y^2 + k^2 - 2xy - 2kx - 2ky = b_d^2 = 4\Delta$, where Δ is the 'parabolic-hyperbolic' form of the discriminant of the quadratic equation, as outlined in section 2.6 above.

4.1. The quadratic sequences in the form of $x = y(y \pm b)$.

From the diagonal of squares, diagonal of oblongs and diagonal (square minus one) numbers, notice how evident it is the diagonal lines $\pm 45^\circ$ with all quadratic sequences in the form of $x = y(y \pm b)$.

Hyperbolas:

$$\begin{aligned} -x^2 + 2xy - y^2 + 2kx + 2ky &= k^2 - b^2 \\ -x^2 - y^2 - k^2 + 2xy + 2kx + 2ky &= -b^2 \\ x^2 + y^2 + k^2 - 2xy - 2kx - 2ky &= b^2 \end{aligned}$$

We have:

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 + y^2 + k^2 - 2yx - 2kx - 2ky &= b^2 \\ x^2 - 2yx - 2kx + y^2 - 2ky + k^2 - b^2 &= 0 \\ x^2 - (2y + 2k)x + (y^2 - 2ky + k^2 - b^2) &= 0 \\ x = \frac{(2y + 2k) \pm \sqrt{(2y + 2k)^2 - 4(y^2 - 2ky + k^2 - b^2)}}{2} \\ \Delta &= (2y + 2k)^2 - 4(y^2 - 2ky + k^2 - b^2) \\ \Delta &= 4y^2 + 4k^2 + 8ky - 4y^2 + 8ky - 4k^2 + 4b^2 \\ \Delta &= 8ky + 8ky + 4b^2 = 4b^2 + 16ky \\ \Delta &= 4(b^2 + 4ky) \end{aligned}$$

$$x = \frac{(2y + 2k) \pm \sqrt{4(b^2 + 4ky)}}{2}$$

$$x = y + k \pm \sqrt{b^2 + 4ky}$$

We know that,

$$(X - Y - Z)^2 = X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 - 2XY - 2XZ + 2YZ$$

So,

$$X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 - 2XY - 2XZ - 2YZ = (X - Y - Z)^2 - 4YZ$$

Then,

$$X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 - 2XY - 2XZ - 2YZ = (X - Y - Z + 2\sqrt{YZ})(X - Y - Z - 2\sqrt{YZ})$$

Rotation 45°:

$$x_0 = \frac{x + y}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$y_0 = -\frac{x - y}{\sqrt{2}}$$

If $y_0 = x_0^4 + 2x_0^3 + x_0^2$, then:

$$-\frac{x - y}{\sqrt{2}} = \left(\frac{x + y}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^4 + 2\left(\frac{x + y}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{x + y}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2$$

$$-\frac{x - y}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{1}{4}(x + y)^4 + \frac{(x + y)^3}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{2}(x + y)^2$$

$$\frac{1}{4}(x + y)^4 + \frac{(x + y)^3}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{2}(x + y)^2 + \frac{x - y}{\sqrt{2}} = 0$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}(x + y)^4 + (x + y)^3 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(x + y)^2 + x - y = 0$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}(x^4 + 4x^3y + 6x^2y^2 + 4xy^3 + y^4) + (x^3 + 3x^2y + 3xy^2 + y^3)$$

$$+ \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(x^2 + 2xy + y^2) + x - y = 0$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}x^4 + \sqrt{2}x^3y + \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{2}x^2y^2 + \sqrt{2}xy^3 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}y^4 + x^3 + 3x^2y + 3xy^2 + y^3 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}x^2 + \sqrt{2}xy$$

$$+ \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}y^2 + x - y = 0$$

$$-\frac{x - y}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{x^4}{4} + x^3y + \frac{3x^2y^2}{2} + xy^3 + \frac{y^4}{4} + \frac{x^3}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{3x^2y}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{3xy^2}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{y^3}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{x^2}{2} + xy + \frac{y^2}{2}$$

5. Subject: Update and Expansion Announcement: "Universe of Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT)"

To: Members of the Mersenne Forum

Dear Mersenne Forum Members,

Title: Launch of New VMTs Tables and Invitation to Collaborate on Automation Software

I am both excited and profoundly astonished to announce the next stage of my project, "Universe of Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT)." This journey, which has captivated me for several years, has led to a revelation that fills me with wonder: the multiplication table, an ancient tool and one of the first mathematical concepts we learn as children, harbors an infinite array of variations. The discovery of this untapped complexity within something so familiar and trivial is truly remarkable. This new phase introduces an array of novel VMTs tables, each revealing a unique aspect of this age-old tool, and represents a significant advance towards the automation of the generation of these tables and figures. It is a testament to the endless depths and surprises that the world of mathematics holds, even in its most fundamental elements.

Names of New VMTs Figures for the standard FMT trio {0,0,0}:

C001830 Square Numbers Lattice-Grid

C001830 Square Numbers MT Hyperbolic Coordinates

C001860 Square Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par.Hyp 1

C001860 Square Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par.Hyp 2

C001831 Oblong Numbers Lattice-Grid

C001831 Oblong Numbers MT Hyperbolic Coordinates

C001861 Oblong Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par.Hyp 1

C001861 Oblong Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par.Hyp 2

C001832 Square-1 Numbers Lattice-Grid

C001832 Square-1 Numbers MT Hyperbolic Coordinates

C001862 Square-1 Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par.Hyp 1

C001862 Square-1 Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par.Hyp 2

C001833 Oblong-2 Numbers Lattice-Grid

Title: C001855 The Distribution of Composites in Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT) – Author: Charles

C001833 Oblong–2 Numbers MT Hyperbolic Coordinates
C001863 Oblong–2 Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par-Hyp 1
C001863 Oblong–2 Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par-Hyp 2

C001834 Square–4 Numbers Lattice-Grid
C001834 Square–4 Numbers MT Hyperbolic Coordinates
C001864 Square–4 Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par.Hyp 1
C001864 Square–4 Numbers Modular Hyperbolic Coordinates Par.Hyp 2

These tables represent a significant addition to the field, offering new perspectives and insights into the fascinating world of Number Theory.

These tables will be added sequentially to the ‘C001202 The SOM numbers’ thread on the Mersenne Forum: <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28116>. I encourage all interested reader to visit this link for detailed views and discussions on each table.

5.1. Important Resource – “The Distribution of Composites in Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT)”:

For those keen on understanding the mathematical foundation and calculations behind this project, I highly recommend consulting "The Distribution of Composites in Variant Multiplication Tables (VMT)". This preprint, available at [Zenodo] (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443439>) or (<https://zenodo.org/search?q=charles%20kusniec&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>), contains essential explanations and calculations that are fundamental to our exploration and understanding of these sequences.

5.2. Automation Project:

Aiming to elevate this project further, I propose the development of parametrizable software for the complete automation of these tables and figures. This software will allow flexible adjustments in variables and coverage of the XY plane and could potentially extend to 3D representations.

5.3. Invitation to Collaborate:

I invite software developers, mathematicians, and data visualization enthusiasts to join this ambitious endeavor. Your expertise can significantly contribute to creating a powerful tool that will transform how we explore polynomial integer sequences.

5.4. Desired Features:

- Automatic generation of figures and tables.
- Integration with the OEIS database for direct referencing.
- An intuitive graphical user interface for exploration and visualization.
- Capability for 3D representation expansion.

5.5. Proposals and Contributions:

I welcome proposals and contributions in any form, including code, ideas, or feedback. A dedicated space on the Mersenne Forum for these discussions could greatly facilitate collaboration and the sharing of knowledge.

5.6. Acknowledgments and Expectations:

I appreciate your support and engagement. Together, we can push the boundaries of mathematical knowledge and open new avenues for discovery in this fascinating field.

5.7. Contact for Collaboration:

Please reach out to me directly through this forum or by email to discuss potential collaborations or propose solutions.

Sincerely,

Charles Kusniec

Acknowledgments

I extend my deepest gratitude to Mr. H. Bli Shem and my Family for their unwavering support and constant inspiration throughout this journey. As a Talmud proverb profoundly states, “*He who does not teach his son a trade teaches him to steal.*” Among the wisest of trades is the pursuit of knowledge through study. I dedicate these studies to my beloved children.

References

- [1] Aaronson, Scott. (2003) “The prime Facts: From Euclid to AKS”, available online at <http://www.scottaaronson.com/writings/prime.pdf>.
- [2] Abdul-Baki, Bassam. (2005) "Extended Midy's Theorem", available online at http://www.abdulkaki.org/math/midys_theorem.pdf.
- [3] Babbage, Charles. (1791-1871) "Babbage's Difference Engine, Principle of the difference Engines", CHM Computer History Museum, available online at <https://www.computerhistory.org/babbage/howitworks>.
- [4] Belden, Otto. "Going's on of Otto's Pastimes", available online at <http://ottobelden.blogspot.com/2010/10/number-sequences-with-ms-excel-visual.html>.
- [5] Caldwell, Chris K. (20xx) "Prime Curios!", available online at <https://primes.utm.edu/curios/>.
- [6] Cox, David N. (2008) "Visualizing the Sieve of Eratosthenes". Notices of the American Mathematical Society. Volume 55, issue 5, page 579, available online at <https://www.ams.org/notices/200805/tx080500579p.pdf>.
- [7] Crawford, Tom. (2023) “Parabolic Mirrors – Numberphile”. Available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oSXVmuNIfRI&t=459s>.
- [8] Evard, Jean-Claude. (2018) "How to find central pairs of complementary divisors of n?", <https://www.researchgate.net/post/How-to-find-central-pairs-of-complementary-divisors-of-n>.
- [9] Gang, Xiao. "Two squares", available online at http://wims.unice.fr/~wims/en_tool~number~twosquares.en.html.
- [10] Gathen, Joachim & Gerhard, Jürgen. (1997). Fast Algorithms for Taylor Shifts and Certain Difference Equations. Proceedings of the International Symposium on Symbolic and Algebraic Computation, ISSAC. 40-47. 10.1145/258726.258745. Available online at file:///C:/Users/charl/Downloads/Fast_Algorithms_for_Taylor_Shifts_and_Certain_Diff.pdf.

- [11] Gil, Juan B. and Weiner, Michael D. (2006) "On Cyclic Numbers and an Extension of Midy's Theorem", <https://arxiv.org/abs/math/0605347>.
- [12] Grime, James. (2013) "Prime Spirals - Numberphile", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iFuR97YcSLM>.
- [13] Gupta, Ankit. (2005) "Decimal Expansion of $1/P$ and Subgroup Sums", available online at <https://www.emis.de/journals/INTEGERS/papers/f19/f19.pdf>.
- [14] Iniguez, Jose C. (2016) "The Golden Quadratic and the Fibonacci System III", available online at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/293175494_The_Golden_Quadratic_and_the_Fibonacci_System_III.
- [15] Johnson, Jeremy R. and Krandick, Werner and Ruslanov, Anatole D. (2005) "Architecture-Aware Classical Taylor Shift by 1", available online at <https://www.cs.drexel.edu/files/ts467/DU-CS-05-06.pdf>.
- [16] Jones, Gareth A. and Jones, J. Mary, "Elementary Number Theory", Springer, 1998; pp. 221-222.
- [17] Kircheri, P. Athanasii. (1664) "Mundus Subterraneus", pg. 24, https://archive.org/details/athanasiikircher00kirc_4/page/n53/mode/2up?ref=ol&view=theater.
- [18] Klauber, Laurence Monroe. (1931), "Klauber's Triangle" pg. 362 available online at <https://archive.org/stream/1931fieldnotesla00klau#page/362/mode/1up>.
- [19] Knill, Oliver. (Jun 19, 2016) "Some Experiments in Number Theory", available online at <http://people.math.harvard.edu/~knill/primes/papers/gaussian.pdf>.
- [20] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Symbolic Conventions and Lexicon. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10127987>.
- [21] Kusniec, Charles (2023). Exploring Hyperbolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10258328>.
- [22] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors (MID) Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252480>.
- [23] Kusniec, Charles (2023). The SOM Numbers (part I). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208029>.
- [24] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The TSP - Triangular Sieve of Primes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10155610>.
- [25] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Divisor Trek. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10128279>.

- [26] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Integers are only Primes and Composites. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419643>.
- [27] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). Shift, Symmetry, and Asymmetry in Polynomial Sequences. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433336>.
- [28] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (HSP). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8419575>.
- [29] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The Modular Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (MHSP). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10109568>.
- [30] Kusniec, Charles. (2023). The Polynomial Simplest Equations, the Symmetry Point, the Two Simplest Recurrence Equations, and the Method of Differences. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8434817>.
- [31] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Conventions, Notations, and Abbreviations", EasyChair preprint no. 4554, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/4ZDm>.
- [32] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Hyperboctys", EasyChair preprint no. 4553, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/RNvX>.
- [33] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Offset in Quadratics", EasyChair preprint no. 4428, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/FQgX>.
- [34] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Paraboctys (part 1)", EasyChair preprint no. 4430, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/rSJd>.
- [35] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Paraboctys (part 2)", EasyChair preprint no. 4482, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/7n9N>.
- [36] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Paraboctys (part 3)", EasyChair preprint no. 4555, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/hd87>.
- [37] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "Quadratics Classification", EasyChair preprint no. 4429, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/KRpp>.
- [38] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The adjustable hyperbolic paraboloid framework of the integer numbers (Part 1)", EasyChair preprint no. 4667, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/Ps32>.
- [39] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The adjustable hyperbolic paraboloid framework of the integer numbers (Part 2)", EasyChair preprint no. 4733, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/l731>.
- [40] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes and Divisors", EasyChair preprint no. 4426, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/ICgH>.
- [41] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes and Products xy ", EasyChair preprint no. 4427, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/SbFH>.

- [42] Kusniec, Charles. (2020) "The Polynomial Simplest Equations, the Symmetry Point, the Two Simplest Recurrence Equations, and the Method of Differences", EasyChair preprint no. 4423, available online at <https://easychair.org/publications/preprint/qr3P>.
- [43] Lauritzen, Bill. "The Social Applications of Highly Composite Numbers", available online at <http://www.earth360.com/math-versatile.html>.
- [44] Lewittes, Joseph. (2007) "Midy's Theorem for Periodic Decimals", available online at <http://www.kurims.kyoto-u.ac.jp/EMIS/journals/INTEGERS/papers/h2/h2.pdf>.
- [45] Lo, Joseph. "Hyperbolic paraboloid", available online at http://www.math.ubc.ca/~cwsei/math200/graphics/hyperbolic_paraboloid.html.
- [46] Loh, Po-Shen. Daily Challenge with Po-Shen Loh. (2019) "Examples: A Different Way to Solve Quadratic Formulas", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XKBOXr3J-9Y>.
- [47] Martin, Harold W. (2007) "Generalizations of Midy's Theorem on Repeating Decimals", available online at <https://www.emis.de/journals/INTEGERS/papers/h3/h3.pdf>.
- [48] Mathematics, StackExchange. (2015) "Meaning of Rays in Polar Plot of Prime Numbers", available online at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/885879/meaning-of-rays-in-polar-plot-of-prime-numbers>.
- [49] Mathematics, StackExchange. (2016) "How to force prime numbers into a line?", available online at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/1291787/how-to-force-prime-numbers-into-a-line>.
- [50] Matiyasevich, Yuri and Stechkin, Boris. (1999) "A visual Sieve for Prime Numbers", available online at <https://logic.pdmi.ras.ru/~yumat/personaljournal/sieve/sieve.html>.
- [51] Medina, Miguel Ángel Morales ([^]DiAmOnD[^]). (2006) "142857: Un número realmente interesante", available online at <https://www.gaussianos.com/142857-un-numero-realmente-interesante/>.
- [52] Medina, Miguel Ángel Morales ([^]DiAmOnD[^]). (2013) "La sorprendente criba de la parábola", available online at https://www.gaussianos.com/la-sorprendente-criba-de-la-parabola/?utm_source=feedburner&utm_medium=feed&utm_campaign=Feed%3A+gaussianos+%28Gaussianos%29.
- [53] Miska, Piotr and Ulas, Maciej, "On Consecutive 1's In Continued Fractions Expansions of Square Roots of Prime Numbers", available online at <https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.03404>.
- [54] Munafo, Robert. (1996-2020) "Numbers A002061, Hogben's Centered Polygonal Numbers", available online at <http://mrob.com/pub/seq/a002061.html>.
- [55] Munafo, Robert. (1996-2020) "Numbers A006542, $C(n,3)C(n-1,3)/4$ ", available online at <http://mrob.com/pub/seq/a006542.html>.

- [56] Nicholes, Will. "Math and numbers", available online at <http://willnicholes.com/math/index.htm>.
- [57] O'Dell, Eric. (1996-2021) "Ulam Spiral Explorer", available online at <https://meresh.com/ulam.html>.
- [58] OEIS Foundation Inc. (2021), "The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences". Published electronically at <http://oeis.org>.
- [59] Paris, Carlos. (2009) "Primal Chaos (Visualizations)", available online at <http://www.sievesofchaos.com/>.
- [60] Pegg, Ed Jr. "Bouniakowsky Conjecture", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource, created by Eric W. Weisstein. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/BouniakowskyConjecture.html>.
- [61] Pegg, Ed Jr. (2006) "Prime Generating Polynomials, Math Games", available online at http://www.mathpuzzle.com/MAA/48-Prime%20Generating%20Polynomials/mathgames_07_17_06.html.
- [62] Pol, Omar Evaristo. (2001-2007), "Sobre el patrón de los números primos", available online at <http://www.polprimos.com/>.
- [63] Pol, Omar Evaristo. (2009-2012) "Links with illustrations", available online in the sequences <https://oeis.org/A027750> , <https://oeis.org/A056538> , <https://oeis.org/A193829> , <https://oeis.org/A212119>.
- [64] Polster, Burkard - Mathologer. (2016) "Infinite fractions and the most irrational number", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CaasbfdJdJg>.
- [65] Rabahy, David. "Google Sheets", available online at https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1GPqipwaQUbD_mPtyJITV8CCJeEjUOKMXz9fVDXAt3Ws/edit#gid=0.
- [66] Ribenboim, Paulo. (2004) "The Little Book of Bigger Primes".
- [67] Ross, Michael M. (2007-2015) "Natural Numbers", available online at <http://www.naturalnumbers.org>.
- [68] Sacks, Robert. (2003-2007) "NumberSpiral.com", available online at <http://www.numberpiral.com/index.html>.
- [69] Sanderson, Grant (3Blue1Brown). (2019) "Why do prime numbers make these spirals?", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EK32jo7i5LQ>.
- [70] Sanderson, Grant (3Blue1Brown). (2023) "The Prime Number Race" - Numberphile, available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YAsHGOWB408>.
- [71] Sato, Takumi. (2013) "Classification of natural numbers and the four sequences", available online at

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358139258_Classification_of_natural_numbers_and_the_four_sequences.

- [72] Schildbach, Wolfgang. "Patterns in prime numbers?", available online at <https://www.fermi.franken.de/wschildbach/primes.html#java>.
- [73] Shannon, A. G. and Leyendekkers, J. V. (2017) "On Legendre's Conjecture", available online at <https://nntdm.net/papers/nntdm-23/NNTDM-23-2-117-125.pdf>.
- [74] Shaw, Mary and Traub, J.F. (1974) "On the number of multiplications for the evaluation of a polynomial and some of its derivatives", available online at <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/321796.321810>.
- [75] Siano, D. B. and Siano, J. D. (1994) "An Algorithm for Generating Highly Composite Numbers", available online at <http://wwwhomes.uni-bielefeld.de/achim/julianmanuscript3.pdf>.
- [76] Sloane, Neil J. A. at Numberphile video by Brady Haran. (Apr 13, 2021) "Eureka Sequences", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6X2D497is6Y>.
- [77] Sparks, Ben at Numberphile video by Brady Haran. (2018) "The Golden Ratio (why it is so irrational)", available online at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sj8Sg8qjOg&t=642s>.
- [78] StackExchange, Mathematics. (2014) "Polynomial shift", available online at <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/694565/polynomial-shift>.
- [79] Stapel, Elizabeth. "Conics: Hyperbolae: Introduction", Purplemath, available from <https://www.purplemath.com/modules/hyperbola.htm>.
- [80] Stapel, Elizabeth. "Finding the Next Number in a Numbers: The Method of Common Differences", Purplemath, available from <https://www.purplemath.com/modules/nextnumb.htm>.
- [81] Unacademy Learning App, (?) "Rectangular Hyperbola", available online at <https://player.uacdn.net/lesson-raw/53KRIOKDC4WS1UKP233U/pdf/9971677413.pdf>.
- [82] Ventrella, Jeffrey. (2007) "Divisor Drips and Square Root Waves", available online at <http://www.divisorplot.com/>.
- [83] Viète, François. (1540-1603) "Formule de Viète", available online at https://edugemath.ch/1re/ch7/ma1-ch7-docs-cours/Ma1_Ch7-degre2_Viete.pdf and <http://serge.mehl.free.fr/chrono/Viete.html>.
- [84] Weisstein, Eric W. "Digital Root", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/DigitalRoot.html>.
- [85] Weisstein, Eric W. "Dirichlet's Theorem", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/DirichletsTheorem.html>.

- [86] Weisstein, Eric W. "Heegner Number", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/HeegnerNumber.html>.
- [87] Weisstein, Eric W. "Lucky Number of Euler", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/LuckyNumberofEuler.html>.
- [88] Weisstein, Eric W. "Powerfree", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/Powerfree.html>.
- [89] Weisstein, Eric W. "Prime Spiral", from MathWorld--A Wolfram Web Resource. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/PrimeSpiral.html>.
- [90] Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, available online at <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Portal:Mathematics>.
- [91] Williamson, John. "Number Spirals", available online at <http://www.dcs.gla.ac.uk/~jhw/spirals/index.html>.